

CORDEX model component description

Version 2.1 (2022-05-16)

This document consists of a summary of the components of the models contributing future regional climate change simulations to the Coordinated Regional climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX, <http://cordex.org>) initiative (Table 1), the institutions and contacts for the simulations (Table 2), and references for all components. Version 1.0 (2021-01-31) of this resource contributed to the IPCC AR6 WGI report (IPCC 2021: AnnexII), see [version history](#). This information has been gathered from the modelling groups initially by the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), aligned with the deadlines and activities of IPCC AR6. The full list of institutions and model names officially registered for CORDEX, including the Terms of Use for the corresponding data, is available at <https://is-enes-data.github.io>.

Table 1: Components of the RCMs contributing future regional climate change projections to CORDEX (see headers for specific components described). An asterisk before the model name indicates that extended information is available through ES-DOC (<https://search.es-doc.org/?project=cordexp>).

RCM Model (* included in ES-DOC and main reference(s))	Downscaling realisation	Domain	Institution	Atmosphere	Aerosols	Land	Ocean	Additional components / comments
				1) number of levels (ToA) 2) dynamics & key parameterizations (reference) 3) details	1) interactive or prescribed 2) component name (reference) 3) details	1) number of levels 2) max. depth (m) 3) component name (reference) 4) details	1) interactive or prescribed SST/SI 2) component name (reference) 3) details	Lake (LK), urban (UR), river (RI) models, etc. Comments on versions/realisations of the same model.
ALADIN52	v1	MED-44 MED-11 AFR-44	CNRM	1) 31 (7 hPa, ~33 km) 2) Grid: Lambert conformal conic projection, hybrid sigma-pressure for the vertical Dyn: Dynamics is computed in the equivalent spectral space using bi-Fourier transforms. Two-time-level semi-Lagrangian semi-implicit numerical integration scheme CU: mass-flux scheme with convergence of humidity closure (Bougeault, 1985) MP: statistical scheme (Ricard and Royer, 1993) with large-scale precipitation by Smith (1990). PBL: Louis (1979) LW/SW: FMR based on Morcrette (1990) and from IFScy15. GHG (H2Ov, O3, CO2, CH4, N2O and CFC) 3) The orographic gravity wave scheme is based on Lott (1999). Interpolation of the wind speed from the first layer of the model (about 30 m) to the 10m height follows Geleyn (1988) .	1) prescribed 3) Szopa (2013) dataset for eval and GCM forcing for scen runs, 5 classes, 2D spatial pattern, vertical profile, seasonal cycle, temporal evolution	1) 3 2) 3) ISBA (Noilhan & Mahfouf, 1996)	1) Prescribed SST 3) ice cover defined by a SST threshold	LK: no UR: Urban areas are considered as rock (Daniel et al. (2019) ALADIN53 is the same as ALADIN52 except for the radiation scheme, which is RRTM for the LW (Mlawer et al., 1997) and FMR-6bands for the SW (Fouquart and Bonnel, 1980; Morcrette et al., 2008), for the turbulent air-sea fluxes (ECUME) and for the mixing length based on Lenderink's work. AFR-44 simulations are not on ESGF, but are available (3 RCP scenarios) upon request.
ALADIN53 Colin et al. (2010) CNRM-ALADIN (2020)	v1	EUR-11						

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				1) number of levels (ToA) 2) dynamics & key parameterizations (reference) 3) details	1) interactive or prescribed 2) component name (reference) 3) details	1) number of levels 2) max. depth (m) 3) component name (reference) 4) details	1) interactive or prescribed SST/SI 2) component name (reference) 3) details	Lake (LK), urban (UR), river (RI) models, etc. Comments on versions/realisations of the same model.
* ALADIN63 Nabat et al. (2020) CNRM-ALADIN (2020)	v1 v2	EUR-11	CNRM	1) 91 (0.01 hPa, ~75 km) 2) Grid: Lambert conformal conic projection, hybrid sigma-pressure for the vertical Dyn: Dynamics is computed in the equivalent spectral space using bi-Fourier transforms. Two-time-level semi-Lagrangian semi-implicit numerical integration scheme CU: PCMT; Piriou et al. (2007) and Guérémy (2011) MP: Lopez (2002) PBL: Cuxart et al. (2000) SW: Fouquart and Bonnel (1980) , Morcrette et al. (2008) LW: based on RRTM (Mlawer et al., (1997) 3) Air-sea turbulent fluxes are derived from the ECUME (Exchange Coefficients from Unified Multi-campaigns Estimates) iterative approach (Belamari and Pirani, 2007).	1) prescribed 3) TACTIC dataset for eval and GCM forcing for scen, 5 classes, 2D spatial pattern, vertical profile, seasonal cycle, temporal evolution	1) 14 2) 3) SURFEX8-ISBA (Decharme et al., 2019) 4) No land use land cover change is taken into account	1) Prescribed SST 3) ice cover defined by a SST threshold	LK: Flake (Moigne et al. (2016)), pronostic lake ice. UR: Urban areas are considered as rock (Daniel et al. (2019)) ALADIN63 v1 and v2 are identical. v2 indicates that the runs driven by the CNRM-CM5 GCM use the corrected version of the CNRM-CM5 Atmospheric-LBCs contrary to ALADIN53_v1
ALARO-0 Giot et al. (2016) Top et al. (2021)	v1	EUR-11 CAS-22	RMIB-UGent	1) 46 2) CU: 3MT (Gerard et al. 2009) MP: Lopez (2002) PBL: pseudo-prognostic TKE (pTKE) scheme based on Louis (1979), see Durán et al. (2014) LW/SW: ACRANEB (Ritter and Geleyn 1992) 3) orographic wave drag based on Catry et al. (2008)	1) prescribed	1) 2 2) 3) ISBA (Noilhan and Planton, 1989)	Prescribed SST	
CanRCM4 Scinocca et al. (2015)	r2	AFR-44 AFR-22 ARC-44 ARC-22 EUR-44 EUR-22 NAM-44 NAM-22	CCCma	1) 25 2) 3) Spectral nudging used to create an open dynamical upper boundary condition for spatial scales larger than 400km.	1) interactive 2) All tracers (e.g. aerosols) have parent-model forcing data on lateral RCM boundaries - even for evaluation run.	1) 3 2) 4.1 m 3) CLASS 2.7	1) Prescribed SST	Full atmospheric physics package identical to that used by parent global model, CanAM4, used by CanESM2 for CMIP5. Historical + RCP8.5 large ensemble (50 members) of 'NAM-44' available for large ensemble (50 members) of its parent model CanESM2.
CCAM Hoffman et al. (2016)	v1	AFR-44i ARC-44i AUS-44i CAM-44i CAS-44i EAS-44i EUR-44i MED-44i MNA-44i NAM-44i SAM-44i SEA-44i	CSIRO	1) 27 (5 hPa) 2) Grid: Global conformal cubic grid with Schmidt transformation. Sigma pressure levels. Dyn: Non-hydrostatic, semi-implicit, semi-lagrangian with reversible staggering CU: Smith (1990) shCU: McGregor (2003) MP: Rotstayn (1997) and Lin et al. (1983) PBL: local-Ri closure (McGregor et al., 1993) LW/SW: SEA-ESF (Freidenreich and Ramaswamy, 1999; Schwarzkopf and Ramaswamy, 1999). Gases (H2O, O3, CO2, CH4, N2O, CFC) 3) No atmospheric nudging.	1) interactive 2) sulfate, black carbon, organic aerosol, mineral dust and sea salt Rotstayn and Lohman (2002) and Rotstayn et al. (2011)	1) 6 2) 4.6 m 3) CABLE (Kowalczyk et al., 2013)	1) Prescribed SST and SI 3) Prescribed SST after bias and variance correction	UR: UCLEM (Lipson et al., 2018) CCAM employed two downscaling methods with CCAM/CCAM-1704 maintaining the change in SSTs predicted by the host GCM but allowed the SSTs to be bias-corrected and decoupled from the atmospheric forcing. CCAM-2008 (see below) used uncorrected SSTs and included atmospheric forcing using a spectral nudging of air temperature, winds and surface pressure at length scales above 3,000 km, essentially replacing lateral boundary conditions with a spectral boundary condition. In this way CCAM-2008 is more constrained by the GCM ensemble, but has less freedom to reduce biases inherited from the GCMs.
CCAM-1704	v1	WAS-44i AUS-44i						

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CCAM-2008 Thatcher and McGregor (2009)	v1	ANT-44i AUS-44i	CSIRO	1) 35 (2 hPa) 2) Grid: Global conformal cubic grid with Schmidt transformation. Sigma pressure levels. Dyn: Non-hydrostatic, semi-implicit, semi-lagrangian with reversible staggering CU: Smith (1990) shCU: McGregor (2003) MP: Rotstayn (1983) and Lin et al (1983) PBL: TKE closure (Hurley, 2007) LW/SW: SEA-ESF (Freidenreich and Ramaswamy, 1999; Schwarzkopf and Ramaswamy, 1999). Gases (H2O, O3, CO2, CH4, N2O, CFC) 3) Spectral nudging of air temperature and winds above 850 hPa as well as surface pressure for length scales above 3,000 km.	1) interactive 2) sulfate, black carbon, organic aerosol, mineral dust and sea salt Rotstayn and Lohman (2002) and Rotstayn et al (2011)	1) 6 2) 4.6 m 3) CABLE (Kowalczyk et al., 2013)	1) Prescribed SST and SI	UR: UCLEM (Lipson et al 2018) RI: Miller (1994) CCAM employed two downscaling methods with CCAM/CCAM-1704 (see above) maintaining the change in SSTs predicted by the host GCM but allowed the SSTs to be bias-corrected and decoupled from the atmospheric forcing. CCAM-2008 used uncorrected SSTs and included atmospheric forcing using a spectral nudging of air temperature, winds and surface pressure at length scales above 3,000 km, essentially replacing lateral boundary conditions with a spectral boundary condition. In this way CCAM-2008 is more constrained by the GCM ensemble, but has less freedom to reduce biases inherited from the GCMs.
COSMOMED	v1	MED-44 MED-11	CMCC	1) 40 2) COSMO- CLM described in Rockel, B., and B. Geyer (2008).The performance of the regional climate model CLM in different Climate regions, based on the example of precipitation, Meteorologische Zeitschrift, 17(4), 487– 498. Steppeler, J., G. Doms, U. Schättler, H. Bitzer, A. Gassmann, U. Damrath, and G. Gregoric (2003), Meso-gamma scale forecasts using the nonhydrostatic model LM, Meteorol. Atmos. Phys., 82, 75-96	1) prescribed	1) 10 2) 11.5m 3) TERRA, multi-layer soil model Heise, E., & Schrodin, R. (2002). A multi-layer soil model including freezing/melting processes. Res Activities Atmospheric Ocean Model, 32, 4-11.	1) Interactive 2) NEMO (Madec et al., 2016) Oddo, P.; Adani, M.; Pinardi, N.; Fratianni, C.; Tonani, M.; Pettenuzzo, D. A nested Atlantic–Mediterranean sea general circulation model for operational forecasting. Ocean Sci. 2009, 5, 461–473. 3) Mediterranean Sea at a 1/16deg horizontal resolution and 71 vertical levels including an Atlantic buffer box	
CCLM4-8-17-CLM3-5 Virgilio et al. (2019)	v1	AUS-44	CLMcom	1) 35 2) CU: Bechtold et al. (2008) MP: Seifert and Beheng (2001), reduced to one moment scheme. PBL: Prognostic TKE (Raschendorfer 2001) LW/SW: Ritter and Geleyn (1992).	1) Prescribed	1) 9 3) CLM (Dickinson et al. 2006)	Prescribed SST	

RCM Model (* included in ES-DOC) and main reference(s)	Downscaling realisation	Domain	Institution	Atmosphere	Aerosols	Land	Ocean	Additional components / comments
				1) number of levels (ToA) 2) dynamics & key parameterizations (reference) 3) details	1) interactive or prescribed 2) component name (reference) 3) details	1) number of levels 2) max. depth (m) 3) component name (reference) 4) details	1) interactive or prescribed SST/Sl 2) component name (reference) 3) details	Lake (LK), urban (UR), river (RI) models, etc. Comments on versions/realisations of the same model.
CCLM4-8-17 Panitz et al. (2014)	v1	AFR-44	CLMcom	1) 35 (30,0 km) 2) Non-hydrostatic regional COSMO model (COSMO model, 2022) CU: Tiedtke (1989) MP: Seifert and Beheng (2001), reduced to one moment scheme PBL: Prognostic TKE closure (Raschendorfer 2001) LW/SW: Ritter and Geleyn (1992) 3) Other: Subgrid-scale orography scheme: Lott and Miller (1997); Schulz (2008)	1) Prescribed 3) Tanre et al (1984) climatology: spatially varying but temporally constant t aerosol distributions are given for rural, urban, desert areas and the sea	1) 10 2) 15.34m 3) soil-vegetation-atmosph here-transfer TERRA-ML (Schrodin and Heise, 2001) 4) deepest soil mid-layer level is 11.5 m; dynamic moisture calculation is restricted to upper 8 levels until 2.86 m	1) Prescribed SST and Sl, no further modification by RCM	LK: no, UR: no, RI: no Simulation carried out by KIT.
CCLM4-8-17 Keuler et al. (2016)	v1	EUR-11	CLMcom	1) 40 (22,7 km) 2) Non-hydrostatic regional COSMO model (COSMO model, 2022) CU: Tiedtke (1989) MP: Seifert and Beheng (2001), reduced to one moment scheme PBL: Prognostic TKE closure (Raschendorfer, 2001) LW/SW: Ritter and Geleyn (1992) 3) Other: Subgrid-scale orography scheme: Lott and Miller (1997); Schulz (2008)	1) Prescribed 3) Tanre et al (1984) climatology: spatially varying but temporally constant aerosol distributions are given for rural, urban, desert areas and the sea	1) 10 2) 15.34 m 3) soil-vegetation-atmosph here-transfer TERRA-ML (Schrodin and Heise, 2001) 4) deepest soil mid-layer level is 11.5 m; dynamic moisture calculation is restricted to upper 8 levels until 2,86 m	1) Prescribed SST and Sl, no further modification by RCM	LK: no, UR: no, RI: no Simulations carried out by BTU and DWD with identical model version and configuration (except vertical layers and ToA) as for AFR-44 simulation above
CCLM4-8-18 Akhtar et al. (2018)	v1	MED-44	GUF	1) 32 (25km) 2) CU: Tiedtke (1989) MP: Seifert and Beheng (2001), reduced to one moment scheme PBL: Prognostic TKE closure (Raschendorfer, 2001) LW/SW: Ritter and Geleyn (1992)	1) prescribed 3) climatology based on MACC product by ECMWF/COPERNIC US	1) 10 2) 15.34 m 3) Multilayer soil model TERRA-ML (Schrodin and Heise, 2001) 4) deepest soil mid-layer level is 11.5 m; dynamic moisture	1) Prescribed SST and Sl	LK: no UR: no RI: no
CCLM4-8-19	v1 v2	MED-44	CMCC					

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CCLM5-0-15 Sørland et al. (2021)	v1	AFR-22 AUS-22	CLMcom-KIT CLMcom-HZG	1) 57 (30 km) 2) Non-hydrostatic regional COSMO model (COSMO model, 2022) CU: Bechtold et al. (2008) MP: Seifert and Beheng (2001), reduced to one moment scheme PBL: Prognostic TKE closure (Raschendorfer 2001) LW/SW: Ritter and Geleyn (1992) 3) Other: Subgrid-scale orography scheme: Lott and Miller (1997), Schulz (2008).	1) Prescribed 3) [AFR] Aerosol optical thickness: NASA/GISS (Global Aerosol Climatology Project, Tegen et al., 1997), accounting for spatial and seasonal variations [AUS] Tanre: Constant aerosol distributions are given for rural, urban, desert areas and the sea	1) 10 2) 15.34 m 3) TERRA-ML (Schrodin and Heise, 2001).	1) Prescribed SST and SL, no further modification by RCM	LK: FLake (Mironov et al. 2010) UR: no RI: no
CCLM5-0-2 Li et al. (2018)	v1	EAS-44	CLMcom	1) 45 2) CU: Tiedtke (1989) MP: Seifert and Beheng (2001), PBL: LW/SW: Ritter and Geleyn (1992) Other: Subgrid-scale orography scheme: Lott and Miller (1997); Schulz (2008)	1) Prescribed: Aerosol optical thickness: NASA/GISS (Global Aerosol Climatology Project)	1) 9 Multilayer soil model TERRA-ML (Schrodin and Heise, 2001)	1) Prescribed SST	Surface roughness: GLOBE (NOAA/NGDC); Global Land Cover 2000 Project (GLC2000)
CCLM5-0-9-NEMOMED12-3-6 Primo et al. (2019) CLM Community (2018)	v1	MED-11	CLMcom-GUF	1) 40 (22,7 km) 2) CU: Tiedtke (1989) MP: Seifert and Beheng (2001), reduced to one moment scheme LW/SW: Ritter and Geleyn (1992) PBL: Prognostic TKE closure Raschendorfer (2001).	1) Prescribed 3) AeroCom Global AOD data is used for Aerosol representation (Kinne et al., 2006)	1) 10 2) 15.34 m 3) Multilayer soil model TERRA-ML (Schrodin and Heise, 2001) 4) deepest soil mid-layer level is 11.5 m; dynamic moisture	1) Interactive 2) NEMOMED12 (Beuviel et al. 2012) 3) 1/12° resolution, 75 vertical levels. The CCLM and NEMOMED12 models are coupled via OASIS3-MCT (Valcke 2013) with a 1-h coupling time step	RI: TRIP (Total Runoff Integrating Pathways) is used as the interactive river component for rivers over the Mediterranean Basin to feed runoff at the river mouths to the Mediterranean Sea (NEMOMED12)

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EBU-POM2c Djurdjevic and Rajkovic (2008, 2010) Krzic et al. (2011)	v1	MED-44i	UNIBELGRAD E	1) 32 2) Hydrostatic, Eta vertical coordinate (Mesinger et al., 1988) CU: Bets-Miller-Janjic (Janjic, 1994) PBL: Mellor-Yamada-Janjic (Janjic, 2003) LW: Chou and Suarez (1994) SW: Chou (1992)	1) Prescribed	1) 4 2) 2 m 3) NOAH-LSM (Ek et al. 2003)	1) Interactive SST 2) POM (Mellor, 2004) 3) 30km, L21, coupling frequency 6 min	LK: no, UR: no, RI: no Same as EBU, but coupled to POM ocean model.
Eta Chou et al. (2014a,b)	v1	SAM-20	INPE	1) 38 (25 hPa) 2) Two-time level split-explicit scheme, hydrostatic, eta vertical coordinate with cut cell orography (Mesinger et al. 2012) CU/shCU: Betts-Miller(1986) modified by Janjić (1994). MP: Zhao et al.(1997). PBL: Mellor-Yamada level 2.5; LW: Fels and Schwarzkopf (1975) SW: Lacis-Hansen (1974)	1) Prescribed	1) 4 2) 2m 3) NOAH scheme (Ek et al., 2003) 4) 12 Vegetation types and 9 soil types.	1) Prescribed SST	LK: no, UR: no, RI: no No orography smoothing; No internal and no lateral boundary relaxation nudging.
* HIRHAM5 Christensen et al. (2007)	v1 v2 v3	ANT-44 ARC-44 EAS-44 EUR-11 NAM-44 AFR-44 EUR-11 EUR-11	DMI	1) 31 (12.5 hPa) 2) Dynamics from NWP model HIRLAM 7.0. Two-level hydrostatic semi-lagrangian semi-implicit scheme. Physical parameterizations are the same as the GCM ECHAM5 (like REMO). CU: Mass flux (Tiedtke, 1989) with modifications after Nordeng (1994) and Pfeifer (2006) LW/SW: Morcrette et al. (1986) with modifications for additional greenhouse gases, 14.6 µm band of ozone and various types of aerosols. Continuum absorption after Giorgetta and Wild (1995). 3) hybrid sigma-pressure coordinate system	1) Prescribed climatology	1) 5 2) 9.8 m 3) ECHAM5	1) Prescribed SST and SI	The different versions v1, v2, v3, are simulation versions due to necessary re-runs, not different model versions.
* HadREM3-GA7-05 Walters et al. (2019) Tucker et al. (2022)	v1 v2	EUR-11	MOHC	1) 63 2) Walters et al. (2019) 3) no lake component, no stochastic physics	1) prescribed 3) MACv2-SP dataset (Stevens et al, 2017), total aerosol properties, 9 bands EasyAerosol (Voigt et al. 2014) RCP scenarios	1) 4 3) Walters et al. (2019)	1) Prescribed SST and SI	LK: no v2 runs are using CNRM boundary conditions from pressure level 3D data. This is because CNRM model level 3D data (used in v1 version) do not correspond to the CNRM output available in the CMIP5 archive. No differences in the RCM, only a different source of atmospheric lateral boundary conditions.

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LMDZ4NEMOMED8 L'Heveder et al. (2013) Vadsaria et al. (2020)	v1 v2	MED-44	LMD	1) 19 2) Li (1999), Hourdin et al. (2006). 3) Coupled to the ocean with daily frequency by the OASIS coupler (Valcke, 2013)	1) prescribed	1) 2 3) ORCHIDEE	1) interactive 2) NEMOMED8 (Beuvier et al., 2010) 3) Interactive Mediterranean Sea only, 9-(120km with a tilted and stretched grid at the Gibraltar Strait, 43 vertical levels with a 6m thick first level.	RI: Interactive river coupling in v2. No river coupling in v1
MAR311 Agosta et al. (2019) Kittel et al. (2021)	v1	ANT-44	ULg	1) 24 2) Hydrostatic (Gallée and Schayes, 1994). CU: Bechtold et al. (2001) MP: Gallée (1995). LW/SW: Morcrette (2002) PBL: E-e (Duyneke, 1988, Bintanja 2000) + MO (Duynekerke and van den Broeck, 1994)	Prescribed, RCP scenarios	1) 7 3) SISVAT (De Ridder and Schayes, 1997; De Ridder, 1997; Gallée and Duynekerke, 1997; Gallée et al., 2001; Lefebvre et al., 2003)	1) prescribed SST and sea-ice concentration; inferred from re-analysis or GCM 3) evolution of the snow properties over sea ice simulated by SISVAT	SISVAT model: 30 snow/ice layers over the ice sheet and two sub-pixels (rocs and permanent ice-covered area)
PROTHEUS Artale et al. (2010) Soto-Navarro et al. (2020)	v2	MED-44	ENEA	1) 18 2) CU: Grell (1993) with the Fritsch and Chappell (1980) closure assumption MP: Pal et al. (2000) LW/SW: CCM3 radiative transfer scheme (Kiehl et al.1996) with specified GHG concentrations PBL: Holtslag et al. (1990)	1) no active aerosol chemical model 2) n/a	1) 2 2) 3) BATS1e (Dickinson et al., 1993) 4) Air-sea exchanges by Zeng et al. (1998) to improve excessive evaporation from warm ocean surfaces (Pal et al.2007) in the original BATS package.	1) Interactive 2) MITMED8 (Sannino et al., 2009) 3) 1/8° resolution	RI: Fully interactive (daily coupling) using the TRIP river routine model
RACMO21P Van Meijgaard et al. (2008)	v1 v2	ANT-44	KNMI	1) 40 2) hydrostatic, with HIRLAM dynamical kernel (Undén et al. 2002) utilizing a 2-level semi-lagrangian advection scheme. CU: EDMF-scheme (Siebesma et al., 2007) 3) Baseline physics is taken from the IFS CY23r4 ECMWF package of physical parameterizations.	1) prescribed 3) Tegen et al. (1997), four classes (land, maritime, dust, urban) + stratospheric + (optionally) volcanic	1) 4 2) 2.89 m 3) TESSEL (van den Hurk et al., 2000) 4) Land-ice tile added for ice-sheet modelling. Multi-layer snow-ice-refreezing scheme (Ettema et al., (2010); snow albedo scheme (Munneke et al., 2011); snow drift scheme (Lenaerts et al., 2013)	1) prescribed SST and sea-ice concentration; inferred from re-analysis or GCM	LK: no, UR: no, RI: no Model versions: Simulations with RACMO21P_v2 are straight reruns of RACMO21P_v1 employing the same model system and parameter settings. In ANT-44 simulations, v2 is only used with MOHC-HadGEM2-ES forcing to fix the remapping of SST to the RACMO grid in the v1-simulation

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				1) number of levels (ToA) 2) dynamics & key parameterizations (reference) 3) details	1) interactive or prescribed 2) component name (reference) 3) details	1) number of levels 2) max. depth (m) 3) component name (reference) 4) details	1) interactive or prescribed SST/SI 2) component name (reference) 3) details	Lake (LK), urban (UR), river (RI) models, etc. Comments on versions/realisations of the same model.
* RACMO22E van Meijgaard et al. (2012)	v1 v2	EUR-11	KNMI	1) 40 2) hydrostatic, with HIRLAM dynamical kernel (Undén et al. 2002) utilizing a 2-level semi-lagrangian advection scheme. CU: EDMF-scheme (Siebesma et al., 2007) shCU: Neggers et al. (2009) MP: Neggers (2009) PBL: TKE (Lenderink and Holtslag, 2004) 3) Baseline physics is taken from the IFS CY31r1 ECMWF package of physical parameterizations. MODIS inferred leaf-area index.	1) prescribed 3) inferred from CAM inventory (except volcanic); historical and RCP pathways (van Vuuren et al., 2011; Lamarque et al., 2010; 2011); also used in evaluation Sulfate, particulate organic matter black carbon, sea salt, desert dust stratospheric aerosols, volcanic aerosol. Spatial maps and vertical profiles per species. Monthly variations and decadal trends.	1) 4 2) 2.89 m 3) HTESSEL (Balsamo et al., 2009)	1) prescribed SST and SI concentration; inferred from from reanalysis or GCM	LK: no, UR: no, RI: no Model versions: Simulations with RACMO22E_v2 are straight reruns of RACMO22E_v1 employing the same model system and parameter settings. Meaning of v2 depends on forcing GCM: i) MOHC-HadGEM2-ES: remapping of GCM-SST to RACMO grid erroneous in v1, corrected in v2 ii) CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5: atmospheric forcings derived from pressure level fields, because of error in CNRM-CM5 model level fields
RACMO22T van Meijgaard et al. (2012)	v1 v2	AFR-44	KNMI	1) 40 2) hydrostatic, with HIRLAM dynamical kernel (Undén et al. 2002) utilizing a 2-level semi-lagrangian advection scheme. CU: EDMF-scheme (Siebesma et al., 2007) shCU: Neggers et al. (2009) MP: Neggers (2009) 3) Baseline physics is taken from the IFS CY31r1 ECMWF package of physical parameterizations.	1) prescribed 2) as in RACMO22E	1) 4 2) 2.89 m 3) HTESSEL (Balsamo et al., 2009)	1) prescribed SST and sea-ice concentration; inferred from from re-analysis of GCM	LK: no, UR: no, RI: no Model versions: Simulations with RACMO22T_v2 are straight reruns of RACMO22T_v1 employing the same model system and parameter settings. In AFR-44, v2 is only used with MOHC-HadGEM2-ES forcing to fix the remapping of SST to the RACMO grid in the v1-simulation
* RCA4 Strandberg et al. (2015) Samuelsson et al. (2015)	v1 v1a v2 v3	AFR-44 ARC-44 CAM-44 EUR-11 NAM-44 SEA-22	SMHI	1) 40 2) CU: based on Bechtold-Kain-Fritsch (BKF) scheme (Bechtold et al., 2001) with revised calculation of CAPE profile according to Jiao and Jones (2008) MP: Rasch and Kristjansson (1998) PBL: TKE scheme (Lenderink and Holtslag, 2004) LW/SW: Savijärvi (1990) and Sass et al. (1994) with the consideration of CO2 absorption and an improved treatment of the water vapour continuum (Räisänen et al., 2000)	1) prescribed 3) single integrated class, parameterized aerosol effect on radiation fluxes, spatially uniform, static.	1) 3 3) a tile-based scheme with physiography based on ECOCLIMAP (Samuelsson et al. 2015)	1) Prescribed SST and SI 3) daily update from driving GCM/reanalysis	LK: Flake (Mironov et al., 2010) pronostic lake ice Model versions: i) v1a is simply a re-run because a restart file to start the scenario experiment was taken from another simulations, ii) v2 and v3 are slightly tuned versions of v1 (some parameters) but parameterizations are the same. SN indicates spectral nudging.
RCA4-SN	v1	ARC-44						

RCM Model (* included in ES-DOC) and main reference(s)	Downscaling realisation	Domain	Institution	Atmosphere	Aerosols	Land	Ocean	Additional components / comments
				1) number of levels (ToA) 2) dynamics & key parameterizations (reference) 3) details	1) interactive or prescribed 2) component name (reference) 3) details	1) number of levels 2) max. depth (m) 3) component name (reference) 4) details	1) interactive or prescribed SST/SI 2) component name (reference) 3) details	Lake (LK), urban (UR), river (RI) models, etc. Comments on versions/realisations of the same model.
RCSM4 Sevault et al. (2014) CNRM-RCSM 2020)	v1	MED-44	CNRM	1) 31 (7 hPa, ~33km) 2) same as ALADIN52_v1 3) Coupled with daily frequency by the OASIS coupler (Valcke, 2013)	1) prescribed (Szopa et al. 2013 dataset for evaluation and GCM forcing for scen runs, 5 classes, 2D spatial pattern, vertical profile, seasonal cycle, temporal evolution)	1) 3 3) ISBA (Noilhan and Mahfouf, 1996)	1) interactive 2) NEMOMED8 (Beuvier et al., 2010) 3) Mediterranean Sea only, 9-12km with a tilted and stretched grid at the Gibraltar Strait, 43 vertical levels with a 6m thick first level.	RI: TRIP (Oki and Sud 1998, Decharme et al., 2010) interactive rivers connecting the atmosphere to the ocean. 50km spatial resolution.
* REMO2009 * REMO2015 Jacob and Podzun (1997) Jacob (2001) Remedio et al. (2019)	v1	AFR-44 EUR-11 SAM-44 WAS-44	MPI-CSC	1) 27 (0 hPa) 2) hydrostatic model built on German Weather Service (DWD) Europa-Modell (EM) weather prediction model dynamics (Majewski, 1991) and ECHAM physics (Roeckner et al., 1996). CU: Mass flux (Tiedtke, 1989) with modifications after Nordeng (1994) and Pfeifer (2006) LW/SW: Morcrette et al. (1986) with modifications for additional greenhouse gases, 14.6 µm band of ozone and various types of aerosols. Continuum absorption after Giorgetta and Wild (1995). 3) hybrid sigma-pressure coordinate system	1) prescribed 3) Tarré et al. (1984) climatology	1) 5 3) Rechid et al. (2009) 4) a tile-based scheme including annual cycle of albedo	1) prescribed SST and SIC	The model releases REMO2009 and REMO2015 differ in internal technical aspects related to refactoring and improving the model code. The physical parameterizations and the implementation of the dynamics are the same. REMO2015 v2 refers to a rerun of the corresponding REMO2015 v1 simulation, which was necessary due to inconsistent model level and surface data in CNRM-CM5 GCM boundary conditions.
ROM Sein et al. (2015)	v1	MED-22 MED-44 WAS-22 SEA-44 EUR-17	GERICS-AWI	1) 27 2) The atmospheric component is REMO CU: Mass flux (Tiedtke, 1989) with modifications after Nordeng (1994) and Pfeifer (2006) LW/SW: Morcrette et al. (1986) with modifications for additional greenhouse gases, 14.6 µm band of ozone and various types of aerosols. Continuum absorption after Giorgetta and Wild (1995).	1) prescribed 3) Tarré et al. (1984) climatology	1) 5 2) 3) Rechid et al. (2009) 4) a tile-based scheme including annual cycle of albedo	1) Interactive 2) MPIOM (Marsland et al., 2003) 3) SST, SIC and SIT are calculated in ocean model	RI: interactive rivers connecting the atmosphere to the ocean. Hydrological Discharge (HD) model with 50km spatial resolution
RRCM Shkolnik and Efimov (2013)	v1	ARC-44	MGO	1) 25 2) hydrostatic CU: Tiedtke (1989) PBL: Meleshko et al. (2014) LW/SW: Shneerov et al., 2001);	1) Prescribed	1) 4 3) MGO-2 (Shneerov et al., 2001)	1) Prescribed SST	

RCM Model (* included in ES-DOC) and main reference(s)	Downscaling realisation	Domain	Institution	Atmosphere	Aerosols	Land	Ocean	Additional components / comments
				1) number of levels (ToA) 2) dynamics & key parameterizations (reference) 3) details	1) interactive or prescribed 2) component name (reference) 3) details	1) number of levels 2) max. depth (m) 3) component name (reference) 4) details	1) interactive or prescribed SST/SI 2) component name (reference) 3) details	Lake (LK), urban (UR), river (RI) models, etc. Comments on versions/realisations of the same model.
RegCM4 Giorgi et al. (2012) Bukovsky and Mearns (2020) Mearns et al. (2017)	v4-4-rc8	NAM-22	ISU NCAR	1) 18 (50 hPa) 2) Hydrostatic dynamical core CU: Grell with Fritsch-Chappell closure over land; Emanuel (1991) over water MP: SUBEX PBL: Holtslag (1990) LW/SW: Kiehl 3) NA-CORDEX (2017)	1) no aerosol effects considered	1) 2 2) 3m 3) BATS1e 4) No subgridding (nsg=1)	1) prescribed SST, no SI 2) surface layer (Zeng et al., 1998) 3) SSTprescribed using atmospheric skin temperature instead of ocean skin temperature	LK: Hostetler et al. (1993) UR: no RI: no
RegCM4-3 Giorgi et al. (2012) Pieczka et al. (2017, 2019a, 2019b)	v1	MED-44	ELU	1) 23 (50 hPa) 2) Hydrostatic dynamical core CU: Emanuel (1991) over ocean, Grell over land, with Fritsch & Chappell (1980) closure. MP: Explicit moisture (SUBEX; Pal et al 2000). PBL: Holtslag (1990) LW/SW: CCM radiation scheme (NCAR CCM3, Kiehl et al. 1998). 3) LBC using relaxation, exponential technique	1) no aerosol effects considered	1) 2 2) 3 m 3) BATS1e 4) Subgridding active (nsg=5 vs default:1)	1) prescribed 2) surface layer (Zeng et al., 1998) 3) no SI	LK: no UR: no RI: no
RegCM4-3 Giorgi et al. (2012)	v1	MED-44	ICTP	1) 23 (50 hPa) 2) Hydrostatic dynamical core (RegCM version 4.3) CU: Emanuel (1991) over ocean, Grell over land, with Fritsch & Chappell (1980) closure. MP: Explicit moisture (SUBEX; Pal et al 2000). PBL: Holtslag (1990) LW/SW: CCM radiation scheme (NCAR CCM3, Kiehl et al. 1998). 3) LBC using relaxation, exponential technique	1) no aerosol effects considered	1) 2 2) 3 m 3) BATS1e 4) No subgridding (nsg=1)	1) prescribed 2) surface layer (Zeng et al., 1998) 3) no SI	LK: no UR: no RI: no Crop stomatal resistance: 45 Crop leaf area index: 6 - rainsnowtemp=1.2 - dPs: 1/10 → 1/20 - d_half (I840, mod_bats_bndry)
RegCM4-3 Giorgi et al. (2012) [SEA] Tangang et al. (2020)	v4	AFR-44 CAM-44 SAM-44 SEA-22 MED-11	ICTP RU-CORE	1) 18 2) Hydrostatic dynamical core (RegCM version 4.3) CU: [AFR-44] Emanuel (1991) over ocean, Grell over land; [CAM-44, SAM-44, SEA-22] Emanuel (1991) MP: Explicit moisture (SUBEX; Pal et al 2000). PBL: Holtslag (1990) LW/SW: CCM radiation scheme (NCAR CCM3, Kiehl et al., 1998). 3) LBC using Relaxation, exponential technique	1) no aerosol effects considered	[SAM-44] 1) 10 3) CLM3.5 [All other domains] 1) 2 2) 2 m 3) BATS1e 4) No subgridding (nsg=1)	1) prescribed 2) surface layer (Zeng et al., 1998)	For SEA-22, in addition on RU-CORE, these institutions also involved in producing the simulations: UKM, VNU-HUS, HUST, MO, AdMU, BMKG

RCM Model (* included in ES-DOC) and main reference(s)	Downscaling realisation	Domain	Institution	Atmosphere	Aerosols	Land	Ocean	Additional components / comments
				1) number of levels (ToA) 2) dynamics & key parameterizations (reference) 3) details	1) interactive or prescribed 2) component name (reference) 3) details	1) number of levels 2) max. depth (m) 3) component name (reference) 4) details	1) interactive or prescribed SST/SI 2) component name (reference) 3) details	Lake (LK), urban (UR), river (RI) models, etc. Comments on versions/realisations of the same model.
RegCM4-3 Giorgi et al. (2012) [CAS] Ozturk et al. (2017) [MNA] Ozturk et al. (2018) [MED] Kahraman et al. (2020)	v5	CAS-44 MNA-44 MED-44	BOUN ITU	1) 18 (50 hPa) 2) Hydrostatic dynamical core (RegCM version 4.3) CU: Grell with Fritsch & Chappell (1980) closure. MP: Explicit moisture (SUBEX; Pal et al 2000). PBL: Holtslag (1990) LW/SW: CCM radiation scheme (NCAR CCM3, Kiehl et al. 1998). 3) LBC using Relaxation, exponential technique	1) no aerosol effects considered	1) 2 3) BATS1e	1) prescribed 2) surface layer (Zeng et al., 1998)	LK: no UR: no RI: no MED-44 (ITU) simulations (Kahraman et al., 2020), nested into HadGEM2, are not on ESGF, but they are available upon request.
RegCM4-3 Giorgi et al. (2012) Torma et al. (2015)	v7	MED-44	ICTP	1) 23 (50 hPa) 2) Hydrostatic dynamical core (RegCM version 4.3) CU: Emanuel (1991) over ocean, Grell over land, with Fritsch & Chappell (1980) closure. MP: Explicit moisture (SUBEX; Pal et al 2000). PBL: Holtslag (1990) LW/SW: CCM radiation scheme (NCAR CCM3, Kiehl et al. 1998). 3) LBC using relaxation, exponential technique	1) no aerosol effects considered	1) 2 2) 2 m 3) BATS1e	1) prescribed 2) surface layer (Zeng et al., 1998)	In addition to default setting, the following modifications were applied: - For crop land use: rsmn=45 (default:200), xlai=6 (default:4) - rainsnowtemp=1.2 (default: 2.2) - dPs=1/20 (default:1/10) d_half (l840, mod_bats_bndry) - critical Richardson number over ocean=0.05 (default:0.25) modifications in: mod_params (Main) mod_runparams (Main/mpplib) mod_pbl_common (Main/pblib) mod_pbl_holtobl (Main/pblib) and in the namelist (pbl parameters were added) (zzhnew only for ocean, vertical profile): if (landmsk(j,i) == 0) then zzhnew = (d_one-zh)*d_r10 else zzhnew = (d_one-zh)*d_rfour end if
RegCM4-4 Giorgi et al. (2012)	v0	EAS-22	ICTP	1) 18 (50 hPa) 2) Hydrostatic dynamical core CU: Emanuel (1991) MP: Explicit moisture (SUBEX; Pal et al 2000). PBL: Holtslag (1990) LW/SW: CCM radiation scheme (NCAR CCM3, Kiehl et al. 1998).	1) no aerosol effects considered	1) 2 2) 3 m 3) BATS1e 4) No subgridding (nsg=1)	1) prescribed SST 2) surface layer (Zeng et al., 1998) 3) no SI	LK: no, UR: no, RI: no Model version: v0 corresponds to the original optimised configuration
RegCM4-4 Giorgi et al. (2012), Sanjay et al. (2017, 2020)	v5	WAS-44	IITM	1) 18 (50 hPa) 2) Hydrostatic dynamical core CU: Emanuel (1991) MP: Explicit moisture (SUBEX; Pal et al 2000). PBL: UW (Bretherton et al , 2004) LW/SW: CCM radiation scheme (NCAR CCM3, Kiehl et al., 1996).	1) no aerosol effects considered	1) 10 2) 3.8 m 3) CLM4.5 4) No subgridding (nsg=1)	1) prescribed SST 2) surface layer (Zeng et al., 1998) 3) no SI	LK: no UR: CLM4.5 RI: no

RCM Model (* included in ES-DOC) and main reference(s)	Downscaling realisation	Domain	Institution	Atmosphere	Aerosols	Land	Ocean	Additional components / comments
				1) number of levels (ToA) 2) dynamics & key parameterizations (reference) 3) details	1) interactive or prescribed 2) component name (reference) 3) details	1) number of levels 2) max. depth (m) 3) component name (reference) 4) details	1) interactive or prescribed SST/SI 2) component name (reference) 3) details	Lake (LK), urban (UR), river (RI) models, etc. Comments on versions/realisations of the same model.
* RegCM4-6 Giorgi et al. (2012)	v1	EUR-11	ICTP	1) 23 (50 hPa) 2) Hydrostatic dynamical core CU: Tiedtke (1996) MP: Explicit moisture (SUBEX; Pal et al 2000). PBL: UW (Bretherton and McCaa, 2004) LW/SW: CCM radiation scheme (NCAR CCM3, Kiehl, 1998).	1) no aerosol effects considered	1) 10 2) 3.8 m 3) CLM4.5 4) No subgridding (nsg=1)	1) prescribed SST 2) surface layer (Zeng et al., 1998) 3) no SI	LK: no UR: CLM4.5 RI: no Model version: v1 is a rerun following a minor bug in boundary conditions
RegCM4-7 Giorgi et al. (2012)	v0	AFR-22 AUS-22 CAM-22 SAM-22 SEA-22 WAS-22	ICTP ORNL	1) 23 (50 hPa) 2) Hydrostatic dynamical core CU: [AFR-22, SAM-22] Tiedtke (1996) land, Kain and Fritsch (1990), Kain (2004) over ocean; [AUS-22, SEA-22] Tiedtke (1996); [CAM-22] Emanuel (1991) over land, Kain and Fritsch (1990), Kain (2004) over ocean. [WAS-22] Emanuel (1991) over land, Tiedtke (1996) over ocean. MP: Explicit moisture (SUBEX; Pal et al 2000). PBL: Holtslag (1990) LW/SW: CCM radiation scheme (NCAR CCM3, Kiehl et al., 1998).	1) no aerosol effects considered	1) 10 2) 3.8 m 3) CLM4.5 4) No subgridding (nsg=1)	1) prescribed SST 2) surface layer (Zeng et al., 1998) 3) no SI	LK: no UR: CLM4.5 RI: no Model version: v0 corresponds to the original per-domain optimised configuration
WRF Skamarock et al (2008) Mearns et al. (2017) Bukovsky and Mearns (2020)	v3-5-1	NAM-22	NCAR UA	1) 28 2) Advanced Research WRF dynamics (Skamarock et al., 2008) CU: Kain-Fritsch-Eta (Kain, 2004) MP: WSM3 (Hong & Lim, 2006) PBL: MYJ (Janjic, 1994) LW: RRTM (Mlawer et al., 1997) SW: Goddard (Chou & Suarez, 1999) 3) NA-CORDEX (2017)	1) Prescribed	1) 4 2) 2 m 3) Noah (Ek et al. 2003) 4) USGS land categories	1) Prescribed SST 3) prescribed sea-ice for GFDL and MPI-driven simulations, sea-ice from SST threshold for HadGEM-driven simulations	LK: no UR: no RI: no Spectral nudging used.
WRF341E Skamarock et al (2008)	v1	EUR-44	NUIM	1) 51 (10 hPa) 2) Advanced Research WRF dynamics (Skamarock et al., 2008) CU: Tiedtke MP: WSM-6 class graupel scheme (Hong & Lim, 2006) PBL: YSU (Hong et al., 2006) LW/SW: RRTMG (Iacono et al., 2008)	1) Prescribed	1) 4 2) 2 m 3) Noah LSM 4) MODIS Land Use categories	1) Prescribed SST	LK: No UR: No RI: No Variable input GHG. E designation was for CORDEX physics ensemble
WRF341I Skamarock et al. (2008)	v2	EUR-44 SAM-44	UCAN	1) 30 (20 hPa) 2) Advanced Research WRF (ARW) dynamics (Skamarock et al., 2008) CU: Kain-Fritsch-Eta (Kain, 2004) MP: WRF single moment 5 class (WSM5, Hong et al., 2004) PBL: YSU (Hong et al., 2006) LW/SW: CAM3 (Collins et al., 2004)	1) Prescribed 3) Uniform background with vertical profile. Constant in time.	1) 4 2) 2 m 3) Noah (Chen and Dudhia, 2001) 4) MODIS land categories	1) Prescribed SST and SI	LK: no UR: no RI: no WRF v3.4.1. "I" stands for the coordinated physics configuration used within CORDEX. "v2" refers to the variable GHG input and noleap calendar in scenario (CanESM2) simulations. Otherwise, fully comparable to v1 in ERA-Interim (fixed GHG, standard cal.)

RCM Model (* included in ES-DOC) and main reference(s)	Downscaling realisation	Domain	Institution	Atmosphere	Aerosols	Land	Ocean	Additional components / comments
				1) number of levels (ToA) 2) dynamics & key parameterizations (reference) 3) details	1) interactive or prescribed 2) component name (reference) 3) details	1) number of levels 2) max. depth (m) 3) component name (reference) 4) details	1) interactive or prescribed SST/SI 2) component name (reference) 3) details	Lake (LK), urban (UR), river (RI) models, etc. Comments on versions/realisations of the same model.
WRF351 Zittis et al. (2014) Zittis and Hadjinicolaou (2017)	v1	MNA-44	CYI	1) 30 2) Advanced Research WRF (ARW) dynamics (Skamarock et al 2008) CU: Kain-Fritsch-Eta (Kain, 2004) MP: WSM6 (Hong & Lim, 2006) PBL: YSU (Hong et al., 2006) LW/SW: CAM3 (Collins et al., 2004)	1) Prescribed	1) 4 3) Noah (Chen and Dudhia, 2001)	1) Prescribed SST	LK: no UR: no RI: no
WRF360J Powers et al. (2017) Evans et al. (2020)	v1	AUS-44	UNSW	1) 30 (50 hPa) 2) Advanced Research WRF (ARW) dynamics (Skamarock et al 2008) CU: Kain-Fritsch-Eta (Kain, 2004) MP: WRF double moment 5 class (WDM5; Lim and Hong, 2010) PBL: Mellor-Yamada-Janjic (Janjic, 1994) LW: RRTM (Mlawer et al., 1997) SW: Dudhia (1989)	1) Prescribed	1) 4 2) 2m 3) Noah (Chen and Dudhia, 2001) 4) USGS land categories	1) Prescribed SST 3) sea ice from SST threshold	LK: no UR: single layer urban canopy model RI: no
WRF360K Powers et al. (2017) Evans et al. (2020)	v1	AUS-44	UNSW	1) 30 (50 hPa) 2) Advanced Research WRF (ARW) dynamics (Skamarock et al 2008) CU: Betts-Miller-Janjic (Janjic, 1994) MP: WRF double moment 5 class (WDM5; Lim and Hong, 2010) PBL: Mellor-Yamada-Janjic (Janjic, 1994) LW: RRTM (Mlawer et al., 1997) SW: Dudhia (1989)	1) Prescribed	1) 4 2) 2m 3) Noah (Chen and Dudhia, 2001) 4) USGS land categories	1) Prescribed SST 3) sea ice from SST threshold	LK: no UR: single layer urban canopy model RI: no
WRF360L Powers et al. (2017) di Virgilio et al. (2019)	v1	AUS-44	UNSW	1) 30 (50 hPa) 2) Advanced Research WRF (ARW) dynamics (Skamarock et al 2008) CU: Kain-Fritsch-Eta (Kain, 2004) MP: WRF double moment 5 class (WDM5; Lim and Hong, 2010) PBL: YSU (Hong et al., 2006) LW/SW: CAM3 (Collins et al., 2004)	1) Prescribed	1) 4 2) 2m 3) Noah (Chen and Dudhia, 2001) 4) USGS land categories	1) Prescribed SST 3) sea ice from SST threshold	LK: no UR: single layer urban canopy model RI: no
WRF361H Skamarock et al. (2008)	v1	EUR-11	UHOH	1) 50 2) Advanced Research WRF dynamics (Skamarock et al., 2008) CU: Kain-Fritsch-Eta (Kain, 2004) MP: Morrison two-moment (Morrison et al., 2009) PBL: YSU (Hong et al., 2006) LW/SW: CAM3 (Collins et al., 2004)	1) Prescribed 3) uniform background with vertical profile. Constant in time.	1) 4 2) 2m 3) Noah (Chen and Dudhia, 2001) 4) Corine Land Cover (CLC) 2006, remapped to IGBP Modis land categories (Bauer et al., 2019); HSWD 30" soil texture (Milovac et al., 2014)	1) Prescribed SST 3) sea ice from SST threshold	

RCM Model (* included in ES-DOC) and main reference(s)	Downscaling realisation	Domain	Institution	Atmosphere	Aerosols	Land	Ocean	Additional components / comments
				1) number of levels (ToA) 2) dynamics & key parameterizations (reference) 3) details	1) interactive or prescribed 2) component name (reference) 3) details	1) number of levels 2) max. depth (m) 3) component name (reference) 4) details	1) interactive or prescribed SST/SI 2) component name (reference) 3) details	Lake (LK), urban (UR), river (RI) models, etc. Comments on versions/realisations of the same model.
WRF381 Pergaud & Castel (2021)	v1	EUR-44 MED-44	CRC-BGS	1) 50 2) Advanced Research WRF dynamics (Skamarock et al., 2008) CU: Kain-Fritsch-Eta (Kain, 2004) MP: Morrison 2-moment (Morrison et al., 2009) PBL: YSU (Hong et al., 2006) LW/SW: RRTMG/RRTMG (Iacono et al., 2008)	1) Prescribed 3) Monthly climatology maps derived from Tegen et al. (1997)	1) 4 3) NoahMP (Niu et al. 2011) 4) MODIS land categories	1) Prescribed SST 3) sea ice from SST threshold	Allow sub-grid cloud fraction interaction with radiation (Alapaty et al. 2012) The forcing variables have been bias-corrected using ERA-Interim fields for 1981-2005, as in Bruyere et al. (2014).
* WRF381P Skamarock et al (2008)	v1 v2	EUR-11	IPSL	1) 31 2) Advanced Research WRF dynamics (Skamarock et al., 2008) CU: New Arakawa-Schubert with deep and shallow convection (Han and Pan 2011) MP: New Thompson scheme (Thompson et al 2008) PBL: MYNN (Nakanishi & Niino, 2004) LW/SW: RRTMG (Iacono et al 2008)	1) Prescribed	1) 4 2) 2m 3) NOAH LSM	1) Prescribed SST and SI	

Table 2: Institution names corresponding to the acronyms in Table 1. Contact e-mail for CORDEX RCM simulations in the corresponding institution (coded by replacing dots by spaces and @ by slash). The full list of institutions registered for CORDEX is available at https://is-enes-data.github.io/CORDEX_RCMs_info.html. This excerpt includes only the institutions providing future scenario simulations.

Acronym	Institution	Contact
AdMU	Ateneo de Manila University, Manila, Philippines	FCruz / observatory ph
AWI	Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research, Germany	Annette Rinke / awi de
BMKG	Agency for Meteorology, Climatology and Geophysics, Jakarta, Indonesia	Dodo Gunawan / bmkg go id
BOUN	Bogazici University, Center for Climate Change and Policy Studies, Istanbul, Turkey	Levent Kurnaz / boun edu tr
BTU	Brandenburgische Technische Universität, Cottbus, Germany	Klaus Keuler / b-tu de
CCCma	Canadian Centre for Climate Modelling and Analysis, Victoria, BC, Canada	John Scinocca / ec gc ca
CLMcom	Climate Limited-area Modelling Community (CLM-Community)	Klima projektionen / dwd de
CLMcom-CMCC	Fondazione Centro Euromediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici. Caserta, Italy, in collaboration with the CLM-Community	Paola Mercogliano / cmcc it
CLMcom-BTU	Brandenburgische Technische Universität, Cottbus, Germany, in collaboration with the CLM-Community	Klaus Keuler / b-tu de
CLMcom-ETH	ETH Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland, in collaboration with the CLM-Community	CORDEX-ETH / env ethz ch
CLMcom-GUF	Institute for Atmospheric and Environmental Sciences, Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany, in collaboration with the	Bodo Ahrens / iau uni-frankfurt de

	CLM-Community	
CLMcom-HZG	Helmholtz-Zentrum Geesthacht (now: Hereon), Germany, in collaboration with the CLM-Community	Burkhardt Rockel / hereon de
CLMcom-KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Karlsruhe, Germany in collaboration with the CLM-Community	Hendrik Feldmann / kit edu
CMCC	Fondazione Centro Euromediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici. Lecce, Italy	Piero Lionello / cmcc it
CNRM	Centre National de Recherches Météorologiques (CNRM), Université de Toulouse, Météo-France, CNRS, Toulouse, France	Contact ALADIN-CORDEX / meteo fr
CRC-BGS	Centre de Recherches de Climatologie, Biogéoscience, Université de Bourgogne Franche-Comté	Albin Ullmann / u-bourgogne fr
CSIRO	Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation	Marcus Thatcher / csiro au
CYI	The Cyprus Institute, Nicosia, Cyprus	G Zittis / cyi ac cy
DMI	Danish Meteorological Institute	obc / dmi dk (O. B. Christensen)
DWD	Deutscher Wetterdienst, Germany	Christian Steger / dwd de
ELU	ELTE Eötvös Loránd University, Institute of Geography and Earth Sciences, Dept. of Meteorology, Budapest, Hungary	Pieczka / nimbus elte hu
ENEA	Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development	Gianmaria Sannino / enea it
GERICS	Climate Service Center Germany (GERICS), Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon, Hamburg, Germany	GERICS-CORDEX / hereon de
GERICS-AWI	Cooperation between GERICS and Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research	William Cabos / uah es
GUF	Institute for Atmospheric and Environmental Sciences, Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany	Bodo Ahrens / iau uni-frankfurt de
HUST	Hanoi University of Science and Technology, Hanoi, Vietnam	Ngo-Duc Thanh / usth edu vn
ICTP	Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics, Trieste, Italy	CoppolaE / ictp it
IITM	Centre for Climate Change Research, Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology, Ministry of Earth Sciences, Pune, India	Sanjay / tropmet res in
INPE	National Institute for Space Research, Brazil	Chou Chan / inpe br
IPSL	Institut Pierre-Simon Laplace, Paris, France	Robert Vautard / Isce ipsl fr
ISU	Iowa State University, USA	akrherz / iastate edu (D. E. Herzmann)
ITU	Istanbul Technical University, Istanbul, Turkey	OnolBa / itu edu tr
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Karlsruhe, Germany	Hendrik Feldmann / kit edu
KNMI	Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute, De Bilt, The Netherlands	vanmeijg / knmi nl (E. van Meijgaard)
LMD	IPSL Dynamic Meteorology Laboratory (LMD)	Li / lmd ipsl fr
MO	Manila Observatory, Manila, Philippines	FCruz / observatory ph
MGO	Main Geophysical Observatory, St. Petersburg	CORDEX / main mgo rssi ru
MOHC	Met Office Hadley Centre	Erasmus Buonomo / metoffice gov uk
MPI-CSC	Max Planck Institute for Meteorology, Climate Service Center, Hamburg, Germany now: Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon	GERICS-CORDEX / hereon de

NCAR	National Center for Atmospheric Research, Boulder, Colorado, USA	Bukovsky / ucar edu
NUIM	National University of Ireland Maynooth	Rowan Fealy / mu ie
OURANOS	Ouranos Consortium on climate change	Paquin Dominique / ouranos ca
ORNL	Oak Ridge National Laboratory	MAshfaq / ornl gov
RMIB-UGent	Royal Meteorological Institute of Belgium and Ghent University, Belgium	CORDEX / meteo be
RU-CORE	Ramkhamhaeng University Center of Regional Climate Change and Renewable Energy, Ramkhamhaeng University, Bangkok, Thailand	Jerasorn / ru ac th
SMHI	Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute, Rosaby Centre, Norrköping, Sweden	Grigory Nikulin / smhi se
UA	University of Arizona, Tucson, Arizona, USA	HChang / atmo arizona edu
UCAN	Meteorology Group, Universidad de Cantabria-CSIC, Santander, Spain	Jesus Fernandez / unican es
UHOH	University of Hohenheim, Institute of Physics and Meteorology, Germany	Kirsten Warrach-Sagi / uni-hohenheim de
ULg	Dpt. Of Geography, University of Liège, Belgium	CKittel / uliege be
UNIBELGRADE	Faculty of Physics, University of Belgrade, Serbia	vdj / ff bg ac rs (V. Djurdjevic)
UKM	Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, Bangi, Selangor, Malaysia	Juneng / ukm edu my
UNSW	University of New South Wales	Jason Evans / unsw edu au
UQAM	Universite du Quebec a Montreal	Winger Katja / uqam ca
VNU-HUS	Hanoi University of Science, Vietnam National University, Hanoi, Vietnam	Phanvantana / hus edu vn

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Version history

Version	Date	Comment
2.1	2022-05-16	Fix COSMOMED entry and supplementary material header note. Set up as a stand-alone document.
2.0	2022-03-11	Major change in the structure. Add CORDEX domains. Split institutions and contacts to a separate Table (2). Split RCM model and downscaling realisation. Add further detail to model components (ToA, physical parameterizations, LSM layers and depth, and extensive reference list for all components).
1.0	2021-01-31	Initial version contributing to IPCC AR6 WGI report (IPCC, 2021: AnnexII: Models).